

Detecting Inconsistent Health Information by Leveraging Abstract Meaning Representation Graphs

Joseph Gatto, Sarah M. Preum

Department of Computer Science, Dartmouth College
{joseph.m.gatto.gr, sarah.masud.preum}@dartmouth.edu,

Abstract

An increasing number of people now rely on online platforms to meet their health information needs. Thus identifying inconsistent or conflicting textual medical information has become a safety-critical task. While there are ongoing efforts to detect fake news and misinformation, they often utilize only statistical features and assume some information is incorrect. However, many individuals receive medical advice that is accurate in the context of one diagnosis yet conflicting or inconsistent with each other, e.g., people suffering from diabetes and hypertension often receive conflicting medical advice on diet. Given two pieces of medical advice, the goal of the medical conflict detection task is to detect and categorize the type of conflict or inconsistency. It is a challenging task, as (i) automatically identifying and categorizing conflicts requires a deeper understanding of the semantics of the text, and (ii) the amount of available data is quite limited.

Prior research focusing on conflict detection uses semantic rule based solutions that require a significant amount of manual effort for data annotation and rule generation. In this paper, we formulate medical conflict detection as a multilabel multiclass classification task in the context of neural language models. We explore the applicability of a state-of-the-art language model, namely BERT, to solve this problem. We introduce the Hierarchical Pair-Wise Encoder for Text Classification (HiPerText), which augments BERT by utilizing Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) graphs for enhanced conflict detection. HiPerText shows promising results for such a resource-constrained text classification task and outperforms BERT by a 40% increase in F1 score on average. We also demonstrate how we can approach BERT-level performance on our pairwise inference task using only information extracted from AMR graphs

Introduction

In recent years, quick and easy access to online health information has changed the way people eat, exercise, and interact with medical professionals (Bujnowska-Fedak and Wegierek 2020). As we continue to live through a global pandemic, people are increasingly relying on online resources for medical advice (Loomba et al. 2021). However, a significant limitation of online health platforms is their in-

ability to provide contextually aware medical advice. Medical advice provided online is most often without consideration of the end-users medical history. For instance, a user is advised to eat foods that interact poorly with their medications or trigger their food intolerance or allergy. Such situations motivate the need for automatic detection of conflicting health information across multiple relevant sources to facilitate safer interactions with online health platforms. This task is referred to as **medical conflict detection** (MCD).

Given two pieces of health advice statements, the goal of MCD is to both identify the presence of a conflict *and* to recognize what type of conflict occurs¹. With more people relying on online health websites and the surge of a global infodemic (Buchanan 2020), detecting inconsistent/conflicting medical information at large is even more critical now, as widespread medical misinformation is a risk to public health and extremely expensive to combat (Cornish 2020).

Different types of conflicts are presented in Table 1. Recognizing the conflict type will aid the user in interpreting the reason for a conflict correctly. For example, consider the quantitative/temporal conflict in Table 1. Simply expressing that a conflict is present does not guide the user on how to react to the conflicting information on fiber consumption. Explicitly stating the conflict type communicates how one should be careful regarding *how much* (quantitative) fiber one should eat as well as *when* (temporal) the fiber should be consumed.

MCD was first introduced in the context of personalized health applications (Preum et al. 2017a,b) where the authors introduce a novel dataset on conflicting medical advice and propose a rule based solution to detect medical conflicts. Although the proposed solution results in high recall (Preum et al. 2017b), the following issues limit its applicability to detect inconsistent medical information at large. First, rule base solutions are brittle and harder to generalize. Secondly, their solution requires a prohibitively expensive amount of annotation for each piece of advice.

The recent advances in transfer learning inspire us to in-

¹MCD does not aim at discounting a source of information as medical conflicts can occur between a pair of advice even when both advice statements are correct (Carpenter et al. 2016). Also, conflict resolution is beyond the scope of MCD as it requires the expertise of a professional healthcare provider and is often subjective to an individual.

Advice 1	Advice 2	Conflict Type
Limit intake of sweetened drinks, snacks and desserts by eating them less often and in smaller amounts.	Many fruits need little preparation to become a healthy part of a meal or snack .	Direct
Limit liquids before bed.	To prevent dehydration, drink plenty of fluids unless your doctor directs you otherwise.	Temporal
Eat Fat-free or low-fat dairy foods such as milk, cheese, or yogurt.	Stay away from refined foods, shellfish, wheat, dairy products and alcohol.	Sub-typical
Eat dark green vegetables such as spinach, collard greens, kale and broccoli	Avoid sudden increase of cruciferous vegetables if you are on Coumadin. They may affect your treatment and dosage	Conditional
Eat healthy foods. Choose foods lower in fat and calories and higher in fiber .	Wait two hours before you eat a high-fiber meal (one with more than about 15 grams of fiber) to ensure absorption of your thyroid medication.	Quantitative, Temporal

Table 1: Example medical conflict pairs from the MCD dataset. Each sample contains a pair of medical advice regarding a common topic. The conflict label is annotated with respect to the common topic between pieces of advice. Conflict topics are bold in the examples above.

investigate pre-trained language models’ applicability to detect medical conflicts automatically. Successful implementation of such a transfer learning based approach can effectively address this critical challenge of automatically detecting inconsistent/conflicting medical information at large. One of the main challenges with using pre-trained language models such as BERT (Devlin et al. 2018) for MCD is that the task is resource-constrained. Furthermore, BERT is not built for multi-sentence inputs and often struggles with capturing long-range dependencies between words.

To alleviate these limitations, we propose the use of Abstract Meaning Representations (AMR) (Banarescu et al. 2013). An example AMR graph is shown in Figure 1 for reference. AMRs encode the relationships between all high-level concepts for a given text. This is useful for BERT as knowledge of semantic relations may help better understand long-range textual dependencies. Evidence of BERT’s need for external semantic information is shown in (Zhang et al. 2020b). Additionally, AMR vocabulary contains concepts and relations that are highly relevant to conflict detection as they explicitly encode relations that are specific to the conflict types. The main contributions of this paper are as follows.

- We introduce the Medical Conflict Detection (MCD) task in the context of pre-trained language models. We formulate the problem as a pair-wise, multilabel, multiclass classification task. We investigate the applicability and limitations of BERT for this safety-critical task.
- We establish the **Hierarchical Pair-Wise Encoder for Text** classification (HiPErText), a pair-wise-graph AMR-based architecture that leverages pre-trained BERT models for multilabel, multiclass disjoint text classification. Our approach outperforms BERT by a 40% increase in F1 score on average. To the best of our knowledge,

this work is the first to successfully encode graphical meaning representation by utilizing non-gold label AMR graphs for disjoint text-paired classification tasks.

While the proposed method of AMR utilization is specific to MCD, we highlight how generated AMR graphs can provide a task-specific prior for any classification task built on AMR-relevant information.

Problem Formulation

Inspired by the definition presented in (Preum et al. 2017b), we define the input to a medical conflict detection (MCD) task as a pair of health advice, (W_1, W_2) each with a common topic or object of an advice, t . MCD is a multiclass, multilabel classification problem. Each advice pair contains one or more of the following labels.

Direct Conflict: Occurs when the topic of a medical advice pair has opposite polarity. If a piece of advice W_i suggests the user take action a , a direct conflict occurs when another piece of advice W_j suggests the user against taking action $\neg a$. In Table 1, our direct conflict example has topic **snack**. We see how advising fruit as a healthy snack directly conflicts with the suggestion to limit sweet snacks.

Temporal Conflict: Occurs when a medical advice pair disagrees about *when* to take some action a . In Table 1, our temporal example agrees one should drink liquids, but disagrees as to when consumption should occur.

Sub-Typical Conflict: Occurs when the topic in reference to the suggested action disagree in type. In Table 1, we see that Advice 2 advises one stay away from dairy in general, while Advice 1 suggests one stay away from high-fat dairy products.

Conditional Conflict: Occurs when a conflict’s occurrence depends on some condition. In Table 1, our conditional

example displays how Advice 1 and Advice 2 are only conflicting if the user is taking Coumadin.

Quantitative Conflict: Occurs when the suggested action *a* disagrees in quantity of the topic/object. In Table 1, we see that Advice 1 and Advice 2 disagree on how much cheese one should be eating.

Non-Conflict: Occurs when two pieces of advice are non-conflicting.

Figure 1: Example AMR graph for the advice “Consume alcohol in moderation.” This graph was generated using a SOTA AMR parser.

Related Work

Abstract Meaning Representation

AMRs are directed, acyclic graphs and encode *who did what to whom* for a given sentence. Unlike other structured text representations such as SRL or dependency trees, AMR graphs have no 1-to-1 mapping between text and semantic representation. AMRs abstract away from low-level syntax and encode solely the relationships between high-level semantic concepts. The abstract nature of this semantic representation has made AMR useful for different tasks, including event extraction (Rao et al. 2017), text summarization (Dohare and Karnick 2017), dialogue modeling (Bai et al. 2021b), and text generation (Wang, Wan, and Jin 2020).

To the best of our knowledge, there is little work on utilizing non-gold label AMR embeddings for pair-wise classification tasks. AMR-based architectures such as (Bai et al. 2021b) have been used for dialogue relation extraction, which takes as input argument pairs to predict relations. However, our work differs from (Bai et al. 2021b) in that the pair-wise nature of our input is *multiple graphs* derived from *disjoint texts*, not multiple arguments extracted from a single graph made from contiguous text. Also, while (Bai et al. 2021b) uses AMR parsers to construct their dataset, they further augment these graphs to create a unified AMR representation for a single dialogue. In this work, we simply parse each advice with no further intervention, demonstrat-

ing how parsed AMRs can easily be injected into various NLP pipelines. However, the general framework outlined in (Bai et al. 2021b) is a useful way to process AMRs for text classification. We modify this framework for MCD and use it as the basis of the HiPErText architecture.

Another related attempt at injecting structured textual knowledge into a disjoint pair-wise text classification pipeline is Syntax-BERT (Bai et al. 2021a), which uses syntactic attention layers to improve the performance of pre-trained BERT models. In this paper, however, we explore the ability of AMRs to encode conflict-specific relations, such as conditionality, topic, and frequency, on MCD.

Medical Conflict Detection

Preum et al. introduced the medical conflict detection task and shared the annotated textual advice dataset collected from health apps and online health websites (Preum et al. 2017b,a). They propose a three step solution to detect conflicts: (i) detecting the semantic tokens (e.g., object of advice, suggested action, temporal clause) of an advice using linguistic rules, (ii) detecting polarity of an advice with respect to the common object of the pair of advice, and (iii) identify and categorize conflict using a semantic rule base that relies on the semantic tokens and polarity of advice extracted in the prior two steps. Their approach is targeted for personalized decision support for people suffering from one or more chronic conditions.

The following issues limit their applicability for detecting conflicting information at large. First, rule base solutions are brittle, and harder to generalize. Secondly, generating semantic rules for complex medical text requires significant manual effort. Finally, their solution relies on a lot of manual annotation of each sample advice statement, including conflict object/topic and semantic tokens of a given advice statement. Such annotation is prohibitively expensive for the ever increasing domain of medical information. These inspired us to explore MCD in the context of transfer learning.

Fact Checking and Fake News Detection

A relevant task is *fact checking*, such as (Kotonya and Toni 2020) who introduce a fact checking approach to online public health claims. However, fact checking differs from medical conflict detection in that fact checking involves use of an explanatory source to confirm the veracity of a claim. Medical conflict detection, on the other hand, does not consider veracity, as two pieces of medical advice can be both accurate yet conflicting.

Fake news detection is another task with similar characteristics to MCD. The detection of fake news can be formulated in a variety of different ways, such as the classification of tweets or entire documents. Further, the output space of a fake news detection problem can be binary (false/true) or multiclass (false/partially-false/partially-true/ true) (Oshikawa, Qian, and Wang 2018). Unlike MCD, detecting fake news is often not formulated as a pair-wise input problem. End-to-end solutions such as (Li et al. 2021) perform well on fake news detection, but are not structured to perform MCD which requires the comparison of two pieces of text.

Solution

HiPErText Architecture

HiPErText is an extension of the hierarchical encoder introduced in (Bai et al. 2021b), which utilizes AMR-graphs to enrich the contextual embeddings provided by a standard BERT model. We now describe how HiPErText modifies the input representation to accommodate pair-wise graphical inputs, as well as a high-level overview of the hierarchical encoder framework, for which more details can be found in (Bai et al. 2021b).

Let $W = \{[\text{CLS}], w_1^1, \dots, w_n^1, [\text{SEP}], w_1^2, \dots, w_m^2, [\text{SEP}]\}$ represent the tokenized pair-wise input for a medical advice pair (W_1, W_2) . For each $W_i \in \{W_1, W_2\}$, we generate an AMR graph $G_i = (C_i, R_i)$, consisting of semantic concept nodes and edge relations respectively. Before introducing the structural information into the model, we first obtain contextual token embeddings from a pre-trained BERT encoder (Devlin et al. 2018), which we denote B .

$$H = B(W)$$

Given contextual embeddings H , we introduce structural information via relation embeddings which are learned during training. To represent the relational embeddings, consider a square matrix $E \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+m+3) \times (n+m+3)}$. E_{ij} thus denotes the relationship between embeddings H_i and H_j , as represented in the AMR graphs. Note that, while there is in general no 1-to-1 relationship between sentence tokens and AMR graph nodes, one can use an AMR-to-Text aligner (Pourdamghani et al. 2014) to *project* the AMR graph onto the sentence. Thus E is derived from this projected graph, allowing us to relate tokens using AMRs. HiPErText then passes the tuple (H, E) through a structure-aware self-attention block, SSA , (Zhu et al. 2019), which uses the relation embeddings to update the attention weights with AMR information. Finally we obtain our AMR graph-structured contextual embedding H'

$$H' = \text{HiPErText}(W) = SSA(B(W), E)$$

As done in the original BERT model, we then utilize the [CLS] token from H' for downstream classification tasks. Furthermore, we also experiment with incorporating our proposed conflict relevant relations into the graph-structured model. While this is potentially redundant information, one can view this as applying a heavier weight to certain conflict-relevant relations. A visualization of both architectures is provided in Figure 2(B).

Integrating Conflict Relevant Relations (CRR)

To incorporate task-specific features, we utilize a list of Conflict Relevant Relations (CRR) derived from the AMR graph of the corresponding advice text. In Table 2, we display our CRRs chosen for each conflict type. CRRs are empirically selected based on their semantic relationship with each conflict type. This is an efficient way to integrate task relevant knowledge to the generic HiPErText architecture.

Conflict Type	Relation
Direct	Domain, Polarity, Topic ²
Sub-Typical	Accompanier, Consist, Sub-event, Example
Conditional	Condition
Temporal	Day-Period, Time, Duration
Quantitative	Degree, Frequency, Quant, Unit

Table 2: Conflict Relevant Relations (CRRs), which are found in the AMR relation vocabulary, shown for each Conflict Type. CRRs are used in the generation of feature vector F_{CRR} , which augments BERT with AMR information.

Suppose we have a graph $G = (C, R)$ where C denotes the set of concepts and R denotes the set of edge relations which define an Abstract Meaning Representation. Let us consider the list R_e , which holds all the edge relation labels, ignoring the concepts on either side of the edge. Note in this formulation we use the term list instead of set as a single AMR graph may use the same edge relation multiple times for a given piece of text. Further, let us denote a function $\text{Count}_A(x)$ which returns the number of occurrences of x in list A . Each element of our relation (F_{CRR}) feature vector is computed as

$$F_{CRR}(i) = \text{Count}_{R_e}(CRR_i)$$

F_{CRR} thus encodes the occurrence counts of relevant AMR relations for a given graph. In this study, since we consider graph pairs, we simply take the summation $F_{CRR} = F_{CRR}^i + F_{CRR}^j$ for a given graph pair (G_i, G_j) . A feature vector as simple as F_{CRR} provides predictive power to the conflict detection task, as the presence of naturally occurring AMR relations can be helpful to understand the conflict type for many samples. For example, if the AMR parser detects a conditional relation between two semantically important concepts, this is often a useful prior for predicting a conditional conflict.

Evaluation Setting

Dataset

Conflicts in the MCD dataset were annotated from real medical apps and health websites which pertain to popular health topics (e.g. nutrition, pregnancy, medicine, etc.). In total, there are 2870 annotated pairs of medical advice statements. We use a train/validation/test split of 2021/213/636 in the experiments conducted in this study. The ratio of single-sentence advice to multi-sentence advice is 0.985. The length of a multi-sentence advice can vary from 2 to 6 sentences. On average, one medical advice is 1.8 sentences long, containing close to 30 words.

The dataset used in this paper is constructed using only information sources that are reviewed by certified medical professionals, thus the number of conflicting pairs of advice statements is fairly low. Also, among the conflicting pairs of advice statements, often the same advice appears in several pairs. This is unavoidable due to the inherent nature of

²This is different from the topic(s) of an advice statement.

Figure 2: Architecture diagrams for our transformer-based experiments. Architecture (A) displays the model corresponding to the BERT baseline, while architecture (B) displays our proposed HiPerText model. Both (A) and (B) can optionally include a linear transformation of our AMR Feature Vector, which we denote as BERT + CRR and HiPerText + CRR respectively.

Conflict Type	Number of Occurrences
Direct	473
Sub-Typical	553
Conditional	524
Temporal	358
Quantitative	68
Non-Conflicting	1363

Table 3: Class label distribution for the MCD dataset. This is a multilabel dataset, thus each conflict type may occur alone or alongside another conflict.

the problem. For instance, there is an abundance of medical advice in favor of cruciferous vegetables, e.g., Kale, Broccoli, Collard greens. However, they might interact with a small set of prescription medications, including Coumadin. Thus there might be multiple conflicting pairs of advice statements on cruciferous vegetables where the advice statements in favor of cruciferous vegetables are different but the advice against cruciferous vegetables is the same. Such as $\mathcal{D} = \{(H_1, H_2), (H_1, H_3), (H_1, H_4)\}$, where each pair has a common topic (i.e., cruciferous vegetables) and H_1 refers to the advice against cruciferous vegetables. Furthermore, it may be the case that multiple samples in \mathcal{D} share the same label. These issues lead to **overfitting** if the training and test sets are not split carefully. This is analogous to the annotation artifacts problem found in standard natural language inference (NLI) datasets, such as SNLI, MNLI, and MedNLI where the labels of many samples can be inferred by looking only at the hypothesis, without observing the premise (Gururangan et al. 2018) (Herlihy and Rudinger 2021).

One potential solution to this problem is the rephrasing of duplicate pieces of advice. Unfortunately, given the multi-class, multi-label nature of the output space, we found that

textual data augmentation strategies struggle to preserve label correctness. Specifically, we tried augmentation strategies such as abstractive summarization (Zhang et al. 2020a), contextual word embedding, natural language generation, and back-translation (Sennrich, Haddow, and Birch 2016). However, none of them preserve label correctness for the majority of the samples. In addition, manual paraphrasing would be an extremely resource-intensive task. These force us to work with limited data and a fixed test set so that we can ensure all singular pieces of advice in the training set are unique from the test set. Furthermore, this formulation prevents us from performing cross-validation. If we use a random split, the model memorizes the label for a single piece of advice and thus results in overfitting.

AMR Graph Generation & Alignment

For each piece of health advice, we parse the text into its AMR representation using a T5-based AMR parser (Rafel et al. 2019). T5 is a text-to-text transformer that allows us to map some advice W to the PENMAN (Kasper 1989) string representation of its AMR graph. The T5 parser is pre-trained on the LDCAMR2020 dataset (Knight et al. 2020), which contains 59,255 gold-labeled AMR graphs.

To obtain the Graph-to-Text alignments, we utilize the Text-to-AMR aligner based on (Pourdamghani et al. 2014), which provides a mapping between textual input tokens and AMR graph nodes. That is, for each node in the AMR graph, we align it with a token in our input sentence W . We use this information to structure input tokens using AMR relations.

Performance Metrics

Given the small number of samples in the MCD dataset, model performance may vary given different random weight initializations. We run each experiment 5 times, each with a different random seed, and report the macro average of all experiments. For each individual experiment, we com-

Model	F1	Precision	Recall
RF	0.01/0.001	0.29/0.03	0.01/0.001
RF + CRR	0.36/0.004	0.48/0.004	0.31/0.005
BERT	0.37/0.08	0.51/0.06	0.31/0.09
BERT + CRR	0.48/0.03	0.48/0.04	0.52/0.05
HiPerText	0.50/0.03	0.49/0.03	0.54/0.06
HiPerText + CRR	0.52/0.02	0.49/0.02	0.59/0.03

Table 4: Comparing HiPerText with BERT and other baseline models. We report the mean/standard deviation over 5 runs of each experiment, each with a different random seed. HiPerText outperforms BERT with a 35% and 74% increase in F1 score and recall, respectively. Also, integrating conflict relevant relations (CRR) significantly improves the performance of each model in terms of all metrics.

pute the weighted F1, precision, and recall scores using the scikit-learn package (Pedregosa et al. 2011). The mean and standard deviation of each set of experiments is reported in Table 4.

Baseline Models

RF: Random forest classifier using TF-IDF feature of the concatenated advice pair.

RF-CRR: To test whether an RF classifier can identify medical conflicts with CRR features. This is a text-free model that is only aware of the relations present in the AMR graphs.

BERT: This baseline uses the default pre-trained ‘bert-base-uncased’ model provided by Huggingface (Wolf et al. 2020). Classification is performed by first getting a contextual embedding given our pair-wise advice input. Next, we use the [CLS] token as described in (Devlin et al. 2018) as input to a linear classifier, which is shown in Figure 2.

BERT+CRR: We append F_{CRR} onto the contextual embedding provided by a pre-trained BERT model for a given medical advice pair. In this baseline we use both the [CLS] embedding and a linear transformation of F_{CRR} as the classifier input. F_{CRR} is added to the baseline models to evaluate how AMR relations effect predictive performance. All neural models (i.e. BERT and HiPerText) utilizing F_{CRR} use an additional batch normalization layer at the time of feature concatenation to ensure proper normalization of our multi-modal feature space.

Bio+Clinical BERT: This baseline aims to test if MCD benefits from medical domain-specific knowledge by using contextual embeddings from Bio+Clinical BERT (Alsentzer et al. 2019). We found that medical knowledge did not enhance performance, as this baseline performed with a mean F1/Precision/Recall of 0.26/0.44/0.20, which is significantly lower than BERT. We omit the use of Bio+Clinical BERT in the remainder of our analysis.

Results

How useful is BERT for medical conflict detection?

In this study, we found that BERT was not sufficient to perform MCD as shown in Table 4. In fact, our experiments show that a simple Random Forest Classifier with *no access to the text* is a more stable conflict detector (i.e. much lower standard deviation) than BERT and closely approaches BERT performance. This result is significant as we show that simple relational information extracted from an AMR parser performs on-par with a 110 million parameter text-based model. We thus conclude that in a limited data setting, text alone is not enough to permit BERT to detect conflicting medical information with reasonable accuracy.

Does incorporating AMR help BERT?

We can directly observe the impact of AMR on BERT through our BERT + CRR model, whose F1 score is 29% better than baseline BERT. It is thus clear that augmenting BERT with AMR produces a significantly better conflict detector. Notably, performance after adding only CRR features highlights how we don’t need to utilize the full graph structure to make AMRs useful to BERT. This drastically simplifies the process required to augment BERT with AMR.

However, we find that utilizing the graph structure further improves conflict detection. HiPerText provides a 4% increase in F1 score compared to BERT + CRR. Interestingly, adding the feature vector F_{CRR} to HiPerText has far less impact than adding F_{CRR} to BERT. This suggests F_{CRR} is already encoding much of the AMR information important to classification.

The best performing model was HiPerText + CRR followed by HiPerText. This highlights the importance of CRRs not only as a feature vector, but as a prior, since HiPerText already has all of the information included in F_{CRR} . In general, performance increased as we add more task specific AMR information, displaying that AMR is well suited to augment and aid BERT in the MCD task.

Are certain conflicts harder to detect?

In Figure 3, we assess which conflict types benefit most from AMR. For four out of the five conflict types, we find that **the more AMR information we inject into the model, the better the performance**. Unfortunately, none of the models are able to predict quantitative conflicts, which have thus been omitted from the graph. This is due to the following two reasons. (i) Although AMRs model relevant quantitative relations, there are few quantitative samples in the dataset. (ii) The quantitative conflicts often require numerical comparison and reasoning and are very difficult to detect.

Identifying **sub-typical conflicts** was challenging for RF+CRR, BERT, and BERT+CRR. These approaches suffer as the AMR relational vocabulary is not best suited for sub-typical conflicts. Relations such as *sub-event* and *consist* are relevant to sub-typical conflicts, but may share properties with other conflict types. The model drastically improves when given access to the full graph, as HiPerText + CRR significantly outperforms other approaches. Detection of **direct conflicts** saw the biggest performance increase when

Figure 3: Analysis of how each conflict type was predicted by each model. Results displayed are the ensemble prediction of the 5 experimental trials reported in Table 4. No model was able to correctly detect any of the quantitative samples.

injecting AMR information into the BERT pipeline. This is intuitive as relations such as *polarity* and *topic* are essential to our definition of a direct conflict. **Conditional** and **temporal** conflicts are accurately classified by the simple RF+CRR model, significantly outperforming BERT and occasionally BERT+CRR. This is intuitive as conditional and temporal are the two conflict types with the strongest encoding in CRRs as shown in Table 2.

Are the proposed solutions sensitive to the length of text?

Figure 4 displays the sensitivity of our proposed model and the baseline models to input length (i.e., combined length of a pair of input advice statements). This is not a direct measure of how AMRs contribute to addressing the long range dependency issue of pretrained language models. However, our results do suggest that AMR allows BERT to interpret longer inputs better. Intuitively, given that HiPerText explicitly links tokens using AMR graphs, it captures long range dependency better than BERT. In summary, Figure 4 shows a significant increase in recall on longer samples when a model uses AMR information. This is also likely in part due to the limitation of BERT to model multi-sentence inputs, something AMR explicitly models.

Limitations and Future Work

A limitation of our work is our dependency on the accuracy of AMR parsers and aligners. We must take the graphs and alignments for granted in this work, as no gold-labeled AMR graphs are available. While this is a limitation, it is also promising that non-gold labeled AMRs can be of such use for the MCD task. In general, parsers may struggle with datasets that have confusing language, non-English text, or very long inputs.

As future work, we plan to collect and annotate more data by including medical misinformation. Furthermore, future

Figure 4: Combined token length of pair-wise input vs mean recall for each bin. This figure shows that AMR-fused models perform better on longer inputs than text-only approaches.

work should consider pre-training the relation embeddings on a separate downstream task using gold-labeled AMR graphs to utilize the structural information better. HiPerText will learn much stronger relational embeddings as the dataset size increases, given these are not currently transferred from another learning task (where BERT embeddings are pre-trained).

Future work should also consider the applicability of this approach to other pairwise classification tasks that may benefit from AMR graph structure, e.g., NLI. Recent works on adding syntactic structure to BERT note that non-gold label syntactic parsings do not add to the predictive performance of pre-trained BERT models (Sachan et al. 2021). However, AMR-BERT shows promising results to explore AMR parsers for various tasks, as they encode rich information at a low cost.

Conclusion

Detecting conflicting medical information can improve the health safety of individuals. In this work, we introduce the medical conflict detection task in the context of pre-trained language models. We provide a thorough analysis of AMRs' ability to help predict medical conflicts and alleviate BERT's issues with resource-constrained inference tasks. Our primary contribution is displaying how augmenting BERT with both simple (CRR) and complex (graph-structured) AMR features can improve predictive performance. Our top-performing model, HiPerText + CRR, outperforms BERT with a 40% and 90% increase in F1 score and recall, respectively. While the CRRs chosen for MCD are specific to this task, the principal idea of this paper, that generated AMR graphs can help downstream classification tasks, has wide-reaching implications for various NLP tasks.

References

- Alsentzer, E.; Murphy, J.; Boag, W.; Weng, W.-H.; Jin, D.; Naumann, T.; and McDermott, M. 2019. Publicly Available Clinical BERT Embeddings. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Clinical Natural Language Processing Workshop*, 72–78. Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Bai, J.; Wang, Y.; Chen, Y.; Yang, Y.; Bai, J.; Yu, J.; and Tong, Y. 2021a. Syntax-BERT: Improving Pre-trained Transformers with Syntax Trees. In *EACL*.
- Bai, X.; Chen, Y.; Song, L.; and Zhang, Y. 2021b. Semantic Representation for Dialogue Modeling. *CoRR*, abs/2105.10188.
- Banarescu, L.; Bonial, C.; Cai, S.; Georgescu, M.; Griffitt, K.; Hermjakob, U.; Knight, K.; Koehn, P.; Palmer, M.; and Schneider, N. 2013. Abstract Meaning Representation for Sembanking. In *LAW@ACL*.
- Buchanan, M. 2020. Managing the infodemic. *Nature Physics*, 16(9): 894–894.
- Bujnowska-Fedak, M. M.; and Wegierek, P. 2020. The Impact of Online Health Information on Patient Health Behaviours and Making Decisions Concerning Health. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(3): 880. 32023828[pmid].
- Carpenter, D. M.; Geryk, L. L.; Chen, A. T.; Nagler, R. H.; Dieckmann, N. F.; and Han, P. K. 2016. Conflicting health information: a critical research need. *Health Expectations*, 19(6): 1173–1182.
- Cornish, L. 2020. Targeting false information on COVID-19: What the funding data shows.
- Devlin, J.; Chang, M.; Lee, K.; and Toutanova, K. 2018. BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding. *CoRR*, abs/1810.04805.
- Dohare, S.; and Karnick, H. 2017. Text Summarization using Abstract Meaning Representation. *CoRR*, abs/1706.01678.
- Gururangan, S.; Swayamdipta, S.; Levy, O.; Schwartz, R.; Bowman, S. R.; and Smith, N. A. 2018. Annotation Artifacts in Natural Language Inference Data. In *NAACL*.
- Herlihy, C.; and Rudinger, R. 2021. MedNLI Is Not Immune: Natural Language Inference Artifacts in the Clinical Domain. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.01491*.
- Kasper, R. T. 1989. A Flexible Interface for Linking Applications to Penman’s Sentence Generator. In *Speech and Natural Language: Proceedings of a Workshop Held at Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, February 21-23, 1989*.
- Knight, K.; Badarau, B.; Baranescu, L.; Bonial, C.; Bardočz, M.; Griffitt, K.; Hermjakob, U.; Marcu, D.; Palmer, M.; O’Gorman, T.; and et al. 2020. Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) Annotation Release 3.0.
- Kotonya, N.; and Toni, F. 2020. Explainable Automated Fact-Checking for Public Health Claims. 7740–7754.
- Li, X.; Xia, Y.; Long, X.; Li, Z.; and Li, S. 2021. Exploring text-transformers in aai 2021 shared task: Covid-19 fake news detection in english. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.02359*.
- Loomba, S.; de Figueiredo, A.; Piatek, S. J.; de Graaf, K.; and Larson, H. J. 2021. Measuring the impact of COVID-19 vaccine misinformation on vaccination intent in the UK and USA. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 5(3): 337–348.
- Oshikawa, R.; Qian, J.; and Wang, W. Y. 2018. A survey on natural language processing for fake news detection. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1811.00770*.
- Pedregosa, F.; Varoquaux, G.; Gramfort, A.; Michel, V.; Thirion, B.; Grisel, O.; Blondel, M.; Prettenhofer, P.; Weiss, R.; Dubourg, V.; et al. 2011. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of machine learning research*, 12(Oct): 2825–2830.
- Pourdanghani, N.; Gao, Y.; Hermjakob, U.; and Knight, K. 2014. Aligning English Strings with Abstract Meaning Representation Graphs. In *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, 425–429. Doha, Qatar: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Preum, S. M.; Mondol, A. S.; Ma, M.; Wang, H.; and Stankovic, J. A. 2017a. Preclude: Conflict detection in textual health advice. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom)*, 286–296.
- Preum, S. M.; Mondol, A. S.; Ma, M.; Wang, H.; and Stankovic, J. A. 2017b. Preclude2: Personalized conflict detection in heterogeneous health applications. *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, 42: 226–247.
- Raffel, C.; Shazeer, N.; Roberts, A.; Lee, K.; Narang, S.; Matena, M.; Zhou, Y.; Li, W.; and Liu, P. J. 2019. Exploring the Limits of Transfer Learning with a Unified Text-to-Text Transformer. *CoRR*, abs/1910.10683.
- Rao, S.; Marcu, D.; Knight, K.; and III, H. 2017. Biomedical Event Extraction using Abstract Meaning Representation. 126–135.
- Sachan, D. S.; Zhang, Y.; Qi, P.; and Hamilton, W. 2021. Do Syntax Trees Help Pre-trained Transformers Extract Information? In *EACL*.
- Sennrich, R.; Haddow, B.; and Birch, A. 2016. Improving Neural Machine Translation Models with Monolingual Data. *ArXiv*, abs/1511.06709.
- Wang, T.; Wan, X.; and Jin, H. 2020. AMR-To-Text Generation with Graph Transformer. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 8: 19–33.
- Wolf, T.; Debut, L.; Sanh, V.; Chaumond, J.; Delangue, C.; Moi, A.; Cistac, P.; Rault, T.; Louf, R.; Funtowicz, M.; Davison, J.; Shleifer, S.; von Platen, P.; Ma, C.; Jernite, Y.; Plu, J.; Xu, C.; Scao, T. L.; Gugger, S.; Drame, M.; Lhoest, Q.; and Rush, A. M. 2020. Transformers: State-of-the-Art Natural Language Processing. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*, 38–45. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Zhang, J.; Zhao, Y.; Saleh, M.; and Liu, P. 2020a. Pegasus: Pre-training with extracted gap-sentences for abstractive summarization. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 11328–11339. PMLR.

Zhang, Z.; Wu, Y.; Zhao, H.; Li, Z.; Zhang, S.; Zhou, X.; and Zhou, X. 2020b. Semantics-aware BERT for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 34, 9628–9635.

Zhu, J.; Li, J.; Zhu, M.; Qian, L.; Zhang, M.; and Zhou, G. 2019. Modeling Graph Structure in Transformer for Better AMR-to-Text Generation. *CoRR*, abs/1909.00136.